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Effect of ICT Integration on Management of Lecturers and Students' Class Attendance in College of Education, Warri, Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated the effect of information and communication technology (ICT) on the management of lecturers and students' class attendance in colleges of education in Delta State of Nigeria. The population of the study consisted 290 subjects: (40 college's administrators, 200 generalist part 2 NCE students and 50 lecturers teaching education courses and general studies courses for part 2 students in all department in the two colleges of education in Delta State). The sample of the study consisted 20 lecturers (10 in experimental group and 10 in the control group) and 50 students (20 in the experimental group and 30 in the control group) and 4 Servicom administrators purposively selected from the college of education, Warri. Three research questions were raised and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The design adopted in this study was the quasi-experimental pretest-posttest non-equivalence control group design utilizing 2x2 factorial design and a fixed factor analysis of variance and covariance-ANOVA/ANCOVA model. A validated structured questionnaire with standardised test items with a Cronbach alpha (α) reliability coefficient of 0.79 was used for data collection. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics (Mean and standard deviation) to answer research questions and the ANOVA/ANCOVA was used to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of statistical significance. Results of data analyses revealed that ICT-integrated based management of lecturers and students' class attendance with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms, significantly improved lecturers and students' class attendance more than when ICT was not integrated to manage lecturers and students' class attendance. The study measured effect sizes, partial eta squared (η^2) of the results to establish the practical significance of the results and found .75, .32, and .01 using Cohen's (1988, 1992) *d* criterion. These effect sizes are large, medium, and small which indicated that practical significance of the results is highly supported. It was concluded that ICT-integration in management of lecturers and students class attendance improved their class attendance significantly and thus improve students' performance. It was recommendations that Federal and state ministry of education should sponsor administrators to attend workshops, seminars and conferences to increase their information and Communication Technology (ICT) awareness and its inclusiveness as administrative management's support tool; to promote effective institution management among others.

Keywords: Administrators; administrative management, tertiary institutions; ICTs; lecturers and NCE students; class attendance.

INTRODUCTION

We are in a world where no one in any works of life can achieve any good scientific and technological innovation without inclusion of the computer and Internet as components of such innovation. Computer and Internet are the two major components of modern information and communication technology (ICT). For about two decades now, computer and Internet which are major computer components of ICT innovation found their way into education organisations in Nigeria and their application in tertiary institutions' administrative management is noteworthy. The benefits of using computers in school organisations, led to the introduction of computer science as a course of study in institutions of higher learning such as the Universities, Polytechnics, Colleges of Education, etc., across continents of the world (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

In this era of technology, we get information update through internet. We take online tickets or use smart cards to take tickets. We do shopping on the internet. We communicate through electronic mail (e-mail), telephones, facsimile (fax), etc. Automatic teller machines-ATM, internet, computers, mobile smartphones, etc. We use these technologies to meet our purpose and to mainly manage information, i.e, to: create, store, disseminate, process information. These are nothing but information and communication technologies- ICTs (Geetar, 2018).

Components of ICT include: computers, television, telephones, radio equipment, CCTV cameras, multi-media, facsimile(fax), communication networks, and know-how. These have a lot of influence in enhancing the effectiveness of instructional techniques and achievement of learning outcomes as well as class attendance management. ICT for school or institution administration and management is divided into three categories: Monitoring instruments (TV, CCTV, Computer); Instructional (Video, DVD, and Multimedia Modules); and Dissemination (TV broadcast, Web conference, e-mail, WhatsApp and Facebook audio and video communication and text messages, Instagram, Twitter messages, etc.). But the emphasis on the choice of technology and the way it is used is partially determined by what is expected in terms of its education administrative management capability, teaching and learning, and improvement in learners' learning outcomes to achieve objectives (Omoghenemuko, 2025).

Information and communication technology (ICT) is used in hospitals, industries, agriculture, banks, cars, aeroplanes, homes, schools, effective administrative support tool for decision-making, everywhere, etc. Information and communication technology (ICT) offers numerous opportunities for changes in various school-related processes like school administrative management, teaching and learning. School administrators with different management styles need modification to integrate the use of ICTs; following emergence of computer networking and Internet requiring school administrators to use computers as a management and administrative tool (Makhanu & Kamper, 2012). Schools should take advantage of these opportunities to introduce drastic changes in education infrastructure, improve skills needed by teachers and administrators to manage education institutions. ICT provides veritable tools for addressing the problems of management of a school system. It suffices to mention that, ICT helps in improving the overall effectiveness of school. ICT-driven schools or academies are suitably referred to as 'Smart schools or academies' today because of ICT-provision for administrators to enhance their administrative support for teachers' efficacy and improved students' learning outcomes (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

Information and communication technology (ICT) is the combination of computers and other data/information processing systems, telecommunication, Internet, broadcasting, multimedia and other associated technologies. ICT promises essential change and innovation in education management as a veritable tool for improving efficiency in both tertiary, secondary and primary institutions; to cope with rapidly evolving global competitiveness; and to effectively meet the challenging management tasks involving flexibility in teaching and learning, and administrative management activities essential in enhancing efficiency and effectiveness in education institutions.

Statement of the Problem

Many tertiary institutions in Nigeria are yet to integrate information and communication technology (ICT) for the administrative management of their institutions, even though ICT integration for school administrative management has proven to be very effective and positively productive for managing lecturers and students class attendance, and this has produced enhanced learners' outcomes in advanced

education environments like the United States of America, United Kingdom, China, Canada among others. Some colleges of education in Nigeria have integrated ICT for institution's administration. Yet, poor academic performance of Nigeria certificate in education (NCE) students across the nation persists. Several research evidence accuses institutions' heads' ineffective management of lecturers and students' activities among others. Hence, this research is motivated within the context of relevance, to investigate the effect of information and communication technology (ICT) on the management of lecturers and students' class attendance in colleges of education in Delta State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the effect of information and communication technology (ICT) on management of lecturers and students' class attendance in colleges of education in Delta State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 level of statistical significance.

1. There is no significant improvement in lecturers' class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education.
2. There is no significant improvement in students' class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education.
3. There is no significant improvement in the management of lecturers and students by college administrators between when CCTV cameras are installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom in Delta State's colleges of education.

Significance of the Study

This study will be beneficial to parents, the students, teachers, and school administrators.

- To the parents, the findings from the study will enable them to have knowledge about their children's classroom activities as it pertains to class attendance, behaviour in class and their level of concentration during lecture periods in colleges of education in Delta State.
- To the lecturers, the study will help them make conscious efforts to teach their courses properly and ensure that the students are motivated to learn since whatever they do in classroom during lesson hours would be seen at a glance by the school administrators in colleges of education in Delta State.
- To students, the study will help them to learn how to comport themselves and be of good behaviour while in classroom or lecturer halls; since their parents would easily be communicated about their classroom activities by school administrators in colleges of education in Delta State.
- To administrators, the study will help the management of the two colleges of education in Delta State of Nigeria to adopt ICT-integrated lecture halls with Internet protocol cameras that will help management through servicom to check lecturers and students' class attendance and classroom activities in other to improve students performance. The study will also help them to have complete knowledge and absolute control of whatever happens in classrooms between lecturers and students during lectures, and take appropriate actions promptly in colleges of education in Delta State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is the technology that promotes the acquisition, storage, retrieval and processing of audio, video, animated images, pictorial, textual, and numeric information into a meaningful and useful form, and the transmission of these information by means of computers, mobile smart phones, social media platforms, and other communication devices via Internet to receivers or users in a specified format for decision-making.

Omoghenemuko (2024) comprehensively defines information and communication technology (ICT) as combination of science and technology that includes the full range of computer hardware and software, telecommunication, computer networks and mobile smart phones, the Internet and Web, wired and wireless networks, digital systems, projector and screen, loud speakers, radio and television, robotics, and video cameras, and so on required for collection and processing of data (texts, video, audio, pictures), and

generating information, and the storing and disseminating of information through the information superhigh-way- the Internet; to different users in a specified format; to facilitate decision-making.

The emergence of ICT has become a driving force for educational reforms, making it possible for school managers, staff, students and parents to exchange information and ideas ease and instantly. This has been witnessed in number of schools having websites and confirmed by Reddi (2011) and Oyieri et al. (2015) who affirm that to assess level of ICT use in education in Kenya, noted that schools are integrating ICT in management of finances, teachers and students, co-curricular activities and infrastructure and human resources management. Oguta et al. (2014) assert that ICT enhances day-to-day management of institutions and enables schools to improve in efficiency and cope with rapidly changing world in executing management tasks. In support of this contention, Ngugi (2012) in an Investigation into the extent of use of ICT in education management in public secondary schools in Naivasha District, Kenya noted that cost-effective application of ICT related technology combined with flexibility in learning and administrative activities is essential in enhancing efficiency in secondary schools. ICT as management tool, has made school management tasks less complex, which according to Mingaine (2013), includes coordination of teaching and learning process, along with educational programmes; financial, human resources and supporting resources; library and information science, and general administration and management. For coordination to achieve educational goals, Alexander (2012) and Oyieri et al. (2015) groups tasks as financial, administrative and instructional management. In financial management in schools. ICT has been used in budgeting, accounting and auditing, which has streamlined financial management and minimized seepage. Again, schools have used ICT in directing and controlling activities which includes staff and students' records management plus stores management and procurement implementation process. Instructional management in schools has used ICT in timetabling, examination management, academic records and teaching-learning process. The study sought to address administrative, financial and instructional management in private secondary schools in Nairobi County.

Information and communications technology (ICT) is an umbrella term that describes any communication device, encompassing: radio, television, multi-media, cellular phones, computer and network hardware and software, satellite systems and so on, as well as the various services and applications associated with them, used for the acquisition, processing and distribution of textual, vocal, pictorial, and audio-visual contents- Such as audio conferencing, video conferencing through the Internet. ICTs are often spoken of in a particular context, such as ICTs in education, health care, business, banking, libraries, etc. (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

ICT for education administrative management is divided into three categories: Monitoring instruments (TV, CCTV, Computer); Instructional (Video, DVD, and Multimedia Modules); and Dissemination (TV broadcast, Web conference, e-mail, WhatsApp and Facebook audio and video communication and text messages, Instagram, Twitter messages, etc.). But the emphasis on the choice of technology and the way it is used is partially determined by what is expected in terms of its education administrative management capability, teaching and learning, and improvement in learners' learning outcomes to achieve objectives (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

The various kinds of ICT products available and having relevance to education, such as WhatsApp video and audio conferencing, YouTube lessons, television lessons, radio broadcasts, interactive voice response system, CD-ROMs, etc; have been used in education for different purposes (Omoghenemuko, 2024; Bhattacharya & Sharma,2007).

On teacher and other staff administration, Alexander (2012) asserted that ICT has enabled allocation of work, attendance, and leave management and performance appraisal, raising efficiency in task distribution, data collection and management. Oguta et al. (2014) note that ICT helps in staff management by processing of voluminous records in a quick, meticulous and impeccable manner, and easing data retrieval. In supporting this position, Mingaine (2013) indicates that ICT can help in providing a good communication system in providing timely information internal and external users acquisition and dissemination in all institutions.

Figure 1
Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework or model in this research shows the relationship between the independent variable (Class attendance Management) and the dependent variable (Class attendance). The independent variable (IV)/ treatment and the independent variable in Figure 1.

METHOD

Research Design

The research design adopted in the study is the quasi-experimental pretest-posttest non-equivalence control group design utilizing 2x2 factorial design and a fixed factor analysis of variance and analysis of covariance-ANOVA/ANCOVA model.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 290 subjects: (40 college's administrators, 200 generalist part 2 NCE students and 50 lecturers teaching education courses and general studies courses for part 2 students in all department in college of education, Warri and college of education, Morsogar, Delta State of Nigeria.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample consisted of 20 lecturers (10 in experimental group and 10 in the control group) and 50 students (20 in the experimental group and 30 in the control group) and 4 Servicom administrators purposively selected for the study from the college of education, Warri. Two groups A and D were randomly selected into experimental group and control group. Group A was randomly assigned to experimental group, while group D was randomly assigned to control group. The experimental group was managed by Servicom management team with CCTV cameras in classroom, while the control group was managed by Servicom management team without- any CCTV cameras in classroom. This sample distribution matrix of the independent variable in the study is shown in Tab. 1

Table 1

Sample distribution matrix of the independent variable in the study

Status	Gender	Servicom Administrator n	Class Management		Row total
			ICT-Based Management (Experimental Group)	No ICT-based Management (Control Group)	
Lecturer III – Chief	Male	4	5	5	10
	Female		5	5	10
Students	Male		7	8	15
	Female		13	22	35
Column Total			30	40	70

Instrumentation

The instrument of data collection was a self-structured questionnaire by the researchers titled: Effect of information and communication technology on management of lecturers and students’ class attendance questionnaire (ICTMLASCAQ). The instrument was divided into three sections: Sections A, B, and C. Section A was designed retrieve information from the respondents on personal data, section B dealt with the questions on lecturers and students class attendance. Section C contained items to determine head of Servicom’s level of management of lecturers and students in lecture classrooms or halls in the two colleges of education in Delta State. The response format of the sections B, and C used a 4-point Likert scale of “strongly agree” (4), “agree” (3), “disagree” (2), and “strongly disagree” (1) based on CCTV footage which is the ICT-integrated management tool employed in this study.

Validation and Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument was face and content validated through expert judgements. Cronbach’s alpha reliability methods was used to determine the reliability of the instrument, by measuring the internal consistency of the instrument using International Business Machine-IBM statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 27, and Cronbach’s alpha reliability methods yielded a reliability index of .79, thus confirming the suitability and reliability of the instrument for the study.

Method of Data Collection

1. Servicom management team goes round to mark class attendance register for lecturers and students 20 minutes into the period for the lecture.
2. Carry out evaluation through the attendance register/watching the CCTV cameras footage to determine lecturers and students class attendance and their classroom attitude.

Method of Data Analysis

Inferential statistic was used for data analysis. The fixed factor ANOVA/ANCOVA was used for analysis of data in the study. Fixed factor ANOVA was used because the level of the independent variables (IV) was not randomly chosen. The effect sizes, partial eta squared (η^2) using Cohen’s (1988, 1992) *d* criterion for independent variable (IV) on the dependent variable (DV) were determined to establish the practical significance of the results of the study (see Table 2).

Table 2
Cohen (1988, 1992): Criteria for Effect Size Measurement

	Cohen’s (1988, 1992) <i>d</i> Criteria for η^2		Cohen’s (1988, 1992) <i>f</i> Criteria for η_p^2
		0.00 - 0.01	Negligible
0.00 - 0.20	Small	0.02 - 0.06	Small
0.25 - 0.50	Medium	0.07 - 0.14	Medium
0.55 - 1.00	Large	0.15 and above	Large

Source: Adopted from Igwebuike, T. B. (in print): Educational Research and Statistics: An Introduction

Procedure

Table 3 Comparison on experimental group and control group

Experimental Group	Control Group
ICT Integration-Based Management (ICTIM)	No ICT Integration-Based Management (ICTIM)
Lecturers' class attendance	Lecturers' class attendance
Students' class attendance	Students' class attendance

Figure 2

Steps in experimental phase of the procedure diagram

Testing of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant improvement in lecturers' class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education.

Table 4 ANOVA on improvement in lecturers’ class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no-ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State’s colleges of education

Group	Posttest Lecturers’ Class Attendance				
	n	Mean	F	Sig.	Effect Size (η^2)
ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms	10	56.76			
			6.84	.00	.75
No ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms	10	47.23			

Table 4 indicates that group has a statistically significant main effect [$F_{(1,9)}=6.84$, $P < .05$, $\eta^2 = .75$]. Table 4 reveals that lecturers’ class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms, had an adjusted posttest lecturers’ class attendance Mean of 56.76 while their counterparts with no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms had an adjusted Mean of 47.23. Despite the fact that the difference between the Means is only slightly significant, it is evident that lecturers’ class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms in experimental group had a higher group Mean of 56.76 than their counterparts in control group no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms with a Mean of 47.23. This result is noteworthy. The effect size (η^2) value of .75 using Cohen’s (1988, 1992) *d* criterion, is large (See Table 2), indicating that practical significance of the results is highly supported.

Based on the results presented in Table 4, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant improvement in lecturers’ class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State’s colleges of education, is rejected. Hence, there is a significant improvement in lecturers’ class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State’s colleges of education, in favour of lecturers’ class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant improvement in the management of students’ class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no-ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State’s colleges of education.

Table 5 ANOVA on improvement in students’ class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no-ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State’s colleges of education

Group	Posttest Lecturers’ Class Attendance				
	N	Mean	F	Sig.	Effect Size (η^2)
ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms	20	77.35			
			5.93	.04	.32
No ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms	30	73.46			

Table 5 indicates that group has a statistically significant main effect [$F_{(1,49)}=5.93$, $P < .05$, $\eta^2 = .32$]. Table 5 reveals that students’ class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms, had an adjusted posttest students’ class attendance Mean of 77.35 while their counterparts with no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms had an adjusted Mean of 73.46. Despite the fact that the difference between the Means is only slightly significant, it is evident that students’ class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms in experimental group had a higher group Mean of 73.46 than their counterparts in control group no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms with a Mean of 73.46. This result is noteworthy. The effect size (η^2) value of .32 using Cohen’s (1988, 1992) *d* criterion, is negligible (See Table 2), indicating that practical significance of the results is highly supported.

Based on the results presented in Table 5, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant improvement in students’ class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State’s colleges of education, is rejected. Hence, there is a significant improvement in students’ class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State’s colleges of education, in favour of students’ class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant improvement in the management of lecturers and students by college administrators between when CCTV cameras are installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom in Delta State’s colleges of education.

Table 6 ANOVA on improvement in the management of lecturers and students by college administrators between when CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and when no CCTV cameras in classroom in Delta State's colleges of education

Group	Posttest Administrators' Management of Class Attendance				
	n	Mean	F	Sig.	Effect Size (η^2)
Management of lecturers and students by college administrators with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms	20	74.61	3.87	.03	.01
Management of lecturers and students by college administrators with no CCTV cameras installed	30	55.27			

Table 6 indicates that group has a statistically significant main effect [$F_{(1,49)}=3.87$, $P < .05$, $\eta^2 = .01$]. Table 6 reveals that management of lecturers and students' class attendance by college administrators with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms, had an adjusted posttest lecturers and students' class attendance Mean of 74.61 while their counterparts with management of lecturers and students' class attendance by college administrators with no CCTV cameras installed in classrooms had an adjusted Mean of 55.27. Despite the fact that the difference between the Means is only slightly significant, it is evident that management of lecturers and students' class attendance by college administrators with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms in experimental group had a higher group Mean of 74.61 than their counterparts in control group were lecturers and students' class attendance by college administrators was managed with no CCTV cameras installed in classrooms with a Mean of 55.27. This result is noteworthy. The effect size (η^2) value of .01 using Cohen's (1988, 1992) *d* criterion, is negligible (See Table 2), indicating that practical significance of the results is highly supported.

Based on the results presented in Tables 6, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant improvement in the management of lecturers and students by college administrators between when CCTV cameras are installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom in Delta State's colleges of education, is rejected. Hence, there is a significant improvement in the management of lecturers and students by college administrators between when CCTV cameras are installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom in Delta State's colleges of education, in favour of improvement in the management of lecturers and students by college administrators between when CCTV cameras are installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom in Delta State's colleges of education.

Summary of Results

1. Hypothesis 1 revealed that there was a significant improvement in lecturers' class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no-ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education, in favour of lecturers' class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms. The effect size of the result in hypothesis one was found to be .75 confirming that the practical significance of the findings of the study is highly supported.
2. Hypothesis 2 revealed that there was a significant improvement in students' class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no-ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education, in favour of students' class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with

CCTV cameras installed in classrooms. The effect size of the result in hypothesis one was found to be .32, confirming that the practical significance of the findings of the study is highly supported.

3. Hypothesis 3 revealed that there was a significant improvement in the management of lecturers and students' class attendance by college's administrators with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms in experimental group than their counterparts in control group were lecturers and students' class attendance by college administrators was managed with no CCTV cameras installed in classrooms with a Mean of 55.27. and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education, in favour of improvement in the management of lecturers and students by college administrators between when CCTV cameras are installed in classrooms and when there were no CCTV cameras in classroom in Delta State's colleges of education. The effect size of the result in hypothesis one was found to be .01, confirming that the practical significance of the findings of the study, though significantly small, is supported.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The result of Hypothesis 1 revealed that there was a significant improvement in lecturers' class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education, in favour of lecturers' class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms. This result is corroborated by the finding of Makewa et al. (2011) who note that ICT had a significant improvement in managing teachers for effective teaching and learning processes. The effect size of the result in hypothesis one of present study was found to be .75, confirming that the practical significance of the results of the study is highly supported.

The result of Hypothesis 2 revealed that there was a significant improvement in students' class attendance between ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms and no- ICT-integrated based management CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education, in favour of students' class attendance with ICT-integrated based management with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms. This result is corroborated by the finding of Dineva and Nedeva (2013) who investigated on how technology influence student attendance and success, and found that information and communication technology (ICT) integration changed the traditional education by creating more meaningful and attractive assignments, increase motivation and lessons attendance, and exam success. This result is also corroborated by the finding Makhani and Kamper (2012) who reported that the integration of ICT for classroom instruction and monitoring instructional progress significantly diminished work load of keeping daily records of students' attendance and generally improved students class attendance and learning outcomes. The effect size of the result in hypothesis one was found to be .32, confirming that the practical significance of the results of the study is highly supported.

The result of Hypothesis 3 revealed that there was a significant improvement in management of lecturers and students' class attendance by college's administrators with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms in experimental group with a higher group Mean of 74.61 than their counterparts in control group were lecturers and students' class attendance by college administrators was managed with no CCTV cameras installed in classrooms. This result corroborates the finding of Ngugi (2012), that effective application of ICT related technology combined with flexibility in administrative activities significantly made school management tasks less complex, including effective administration of teachers and learners than traditional teacher and students' management techniques. The effect size of the result in hypothesis one was found to be .01, though relatively small, it confirms that the practical significance of the results of the study is supported.

Implications of Results of the Study

The results of this study have implications for colleges of education's administrators, teachers/lecturers, education curriculum developers, and researchers in education. The results, in part, indicated that ICT-integrated based management of lecturers and students class attendance significantly improved lecturers and students class attendance, and this definitely snowballs into improved students' performance.

Teacher education curriculum developers at tertiary education level in the departments of curriculum and educational administration, should carry out studies on the innovative application of ICT in administrative and teaching options to find out if it can be included in the National Commissions for Colleges of Education (NCCE) curriculum.

The major purpose of any learning institution is to improve students learning. An implication of the results of this study which indicates that ICT-based administrative management support for lecturers and Nigeria certificate in education (NCE) students is very imperative is that, it promotes lecturers' commitment to their lectures and NCE students' commitment to class attendance, which can lead to improved NCE students' academic performance.

Another implication of the results of this study, is that researchers in management and administration, for the improvement of students learning outcomes, should carry out interdisciplinary studies to explore further, the efficacy of ICT-based administrative support for lecturers' commitment to duty and NCE students' class attendance in promoting improved students' performance.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the study, conclusions can be made on the hypotheses tested. The results from the test of null hypotheses one and two revealed that there was a significant improvement in both lecturers and students' class attendance when lecturers and students' class attendance were managed with ICT-integrated based CCTV cameras installed in classrooms (lecture halls) more than when there was no- ICT-integrated based CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education. While null hypotheses three revealed a significant improvement in management of lecturers and NCE students' class attendance by college's administrators with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms in experimental group than their counterparts in control group where lecturers and NCE students' class attendance by college administrators were managed traditionally with no CCTV cameras installed in classrooms. Clearly, ICT-integrated based management of lecturers and NCE students' class attendance with CCTV cameras installed in classrooms, significantly improved lecturers and students' class attendance more than when no- ICT-integrated was used to manage lecturers and students' class attendance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Federal and state ministry of education should sponsor administrators to attend workshops, seminars and conferences to increase their information and Communication Technology (ICT) awareness and ensure the inclusivity of ICTs as administrative support tools; to promote effective management.
2. Provosts of colleges of education in Delta State should as a matter of urgency, promote regular in-service administrative training of college's administrators on the use of ICT tools to improve their administrative skill. This will improve the overall college's administration.
3. Administrators in Delta State's colleges of education should develop positive attitude towards their job in other for them to be more effective in the discharge of their duties; to promote all overall effective administration of colleges of education in Delta State.

Contribution to Knowledge

The results of the study which investigated the effect of ICT integration on the management of lecturers and students' class attendance in Delta State's colleges of education, indicated undoubtedly that ICT-integrated CCTV cameras installed in classrooms significantly improved both lecturers and students' class attendance more than when there were no-ICT-integrated CCTV cameras in classrooms in Delta State's colleges of education.

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REFERENCES

- Adu, E. O., & Adu, E. O. (2013). The use and management of ICT in schools: Strategies for school leaders. *European Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology (EJCSIT)*, 1(2), 10-16.
- Dineva, S. & Nedeva, V. (2013). How technology influence student attendance and success. ResearchGate. sbdineva@abv.bg
- Fagbohungebe, O. B. (2009). The basics of research methodology. Kotleb publisher, Shomolu, Lagos, Nigeria. ISBN 978-232-261-4.
- Geetar, T. (2018). Concept of information and communication technology (ICT). <https://ebooks.inflibnet.ac.in/ae01/chapter/concept-of-information-and-communication-technology/>
- Igwebuikwe, T. B. (2022). Educational research methods and statistics: An introduction. Chuton Publications, Kwale, Delta State, Nigeria. ISBN 978-133-129-8: 255-262.
- Makhanu, E. & Kamper, G. (2012). The relationship between principals' access to information and communication technology (ICT) and school performance in Kenya. University of South Africa, Pretoria 003. <http://www.heraldjournals.org/hjlegs/archive.htm>.
- Matthew (Damkor), D., Joro, I. D., & Manasseh, H. (2015). The role of information communication technology in Nigeria educational system. *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies*, 2(2), 64–68.
- Mingaine. L. (2013). Skill challenges in adoption and use of ICT in public secondary schools in Kenya. <http://www.ijssnet.com/journals/vol.3-No-13-july-2013/8.pdf>.
- Ngugi, P. (2012). An investigation into the extent of use of ICT in education management in public secondary schools in Naivasha District, K.U.
- Oguta, I. O., Egessa, R. K. W., & Musiega, D. (2014). Effect of ICT application on strategic educational quality standards management in Bungoma county, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 3(5). 11-17
- Omoghenemuko, G. I. (2025). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Education: A global perspective (1st ed.). COEWA Publishers, ISBN 978-33794-6.
- Omoghenemuko, G. I. (2024). Computers and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Education: A global perspective. COEWA Publishers, ISBN 978-33794-6-7.
- Omoghenemuko, G. I. (2024). Effects of transformational leadership in the classroom on NCE educatees' cognitive and affective achievement and self-efficacy beliefs in computer science. A Master Dissertation submitted to the Postgraduate School in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Master in Education (M.Ed) (Educational Administration) in the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, PortHarcourt, Nigeria.
- Omoghenemuko, G. I. (2019). Effect of computer usage on the job performance effectiveness of school administrators and teachers' job performance effectiveness in private secondary schools in Ughelli South Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria (Unpublished).
- Oyieri, C. R., Odundo, P. A., Ganira, K. L., & Wangui, K. R. (2015). Effects of ICT integration in the management of private secondary schools in Nairobi County, Kenya: Policy options and practices. *World Journal of Education*, 5(6).